

Building credibility and visibility in alternative and complementary medicine: A linguistic and discursive perspective

Girolamo TESSUTO, Seconda Università degli Studi di Napoli, Italy

As non-mainstream medical practice is making headway and resisting the dominant discourse of biomedical practice, there is the need to understand how non-mainstream, alternative/complementary scholars provide a credible representation of themselves by creating a convincing discourse from within the boundaries of their discipline while enhancing visibility and impact to stay ahead of competition in today's regime of 'patronage and fear' of academic life. Using a representative corpus of academic articles in this field, I look at how authors 'position' themselves and carve out a distinct knowledge space that reflects their professional identity and promotes the quality and credibility of their own research to the scientific community. To do this, I consider the markers of evaluation and stance in academic discourse analysis for their meaning making, in both quantitative and qualitative terms, and elucidate a context for interpretation, showing how patterns of promotional language are used to enhance visibility of, and attention for, both research and researchers within a super-crowded and competitive world of digital scholarly publishing.

Keywords: Academic Discourse; Attention-seeking; CAM; Complementary and Alternative Medicine; Credibility

1. Introduction

As mainstream biomedical practice continues to dominate the discourse about health, disease and treatment, non-mainstream, alternative/complementary medical practice is moving forward and becoming increasingly visible in scientific journals, where it competes with the might of mainstream research outputs as well as a digital publishing system of 'patronage and fear'. In this system, non-mainstream scholars are not only under immense pressure to publish papers and resist the dominant discourse of biomedicine, but they are also required to provide a credible representation of themselves and their research work using the persuasive patterns of language that rhetorically raise their professional visibility and compete for reader's attention within a super-crowded world of digital scholarly publishing. Although much work has been devoted to interpersonal and evaluative features of language that contribute to academic persuasion in mainstream medical discourse, analyses of non-

mainstream medical discourse that display persuasive practices through an interpersonal and evaluative system of linguistic expressions are largely missing from this research landscape. To bridge this gap, I use a representative corpus of academic articles in non-mainstream medical discourse to examine how authors 'position' themselves and establish a distinct knowledge space that reflects their professional identity and promotes the credibility of their own research to the wider scientific community. I attend to the markers of evaluation in academic discourse analysis for their stance meaning making, showing how patterns of promotional language enhance visibility of, and attention for, both research and researchers, while framing the persuasive practices of non-mainstream researchers who take sides in relation to valid arguments in a context of greater competition in online scholarly publications.

2. Background

At a time when medical pluralism is growing throughout the Western world as part of a globalized health market (Hampshire & Owusu, 2012), the use of a plurality of treatment choices has become a common standard in all Western societies over the past twenty years, making it possible for people to choose both mainstream and non-mainstream approaches to medical care (Shih et al., 2010). While there are several decision factors driving such pluralistic choices, the tangible presence of multiple therapeutic modalities not only provides evidence for different representations of knowledge discourses about health, but also for differently conceived systems and traditions characterized by opposition and labelling.

When it comes to non-mainstream healthcare terms, the comprehensive label 'Complementary and Alternative Medicine' (CAM), is often used to describe a complex system of healing practices and disciplines that fall outside of mainstream or conventional medicine. The US National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health (NCCIH, 2024) describes this overarching term, 'complementary and alternative medicine' (CAM), as "a group of diverse medical and health care systems, practices, and products" that are either used "*together with* conventional medicine" (complementary), such as acupuncture used alongside medications and immunotherapy, or "*in place of* conventional medicine" (alternative), such as homeopathy instead of pharmaceutical medications (*my italics*). Over and above stands 'Integrative Health' (IH), defined as a system that "brings conventional and complementary approaches together in a coordinated way . . . , with an emphasis on treating the whole person rather than, for example, one organ system" and "aim[ing] for well-coordinated care among different providers and institutions" (NCCIH, 2024, p. 1). Yet, to compound matters, we also have 'Integrative Medicine' (IM), defined rather similarly as "an approach to medical care that combines conventional medicine with CAM practices that have shown through science to

be safe and effective . . .” (National Institutes of Health-National Cancer Institute, 2023, p. 1). No matter which term is employed, it is far too obvious that CAM modalities draw upon their ancient healing philosophies, traditions and belief systems developing across different societies and cultures, where “magical or spiritual healing practices and herbal remedies are the oldest traditional systems of folk medicine” (Tessuto, 2024a, p. 2).

What is implied in these definitions is that the very terms used to designate ‘complementary’, ‘alternative’, or ‘integrative’ say as much about the residual nature of such healing modalities as about the hegemonic role held by mainstream, Western ‘biomedicine’ internationally (Baronov, 2008; Davies, 2016; Keating & Cambrosio, 2003). The hegemonic role played by ‘hard-core’, evidence-based logic of biomedical science is in fact so commonplace that there is neither shortage or flaws in understanding biomedicine as a dominant medical ideology that “represents an expression of social power” and “privilege within capitalist societies” (Baronov, 2008, p. 235) in which it inherently “bears a distinct cultural authority” (Davies, 2016, p. 71).

Standing alongside this is the public debate over CAM. Here, biomedical practitioners could be anywhere on the spectrum, from disparaging non-mainstream medicine outright to accepting it to a greater or lesser degree (Beyerstein, 2001; Grandinetti, 2000), with decriers of CAM obviously basing their arguments on Western biomedical notions of ‘truth’ that satisfies the standards of scientific evidence treatment through particularly “randomized controlled clinical trials and their meta-analyses” (Yakoot, 2013, p. 83), thereby providing a polarized understanding of CAM and biomedical knowledge. Despite this, there is a growing awareness that “CAM research” is on the road to “methodological rigour and disciplinary training” and that “evidence-based CAM therapies have shown remarkable success in treating diseases” (Adams et al., 2012, p. 3). In other words, non-mainstream CAM is mature enough to gain from a good dose of empiricism in terms of “evidence-based information sharing” and efficacy in Integrative Medicine therapies (Mortada, 2024, p. 1).

But, any such debate is not without a process of boundary division when the power and authority of biomedicine is exercised within its own professional field. As a matter of fact, earlier studies in sociology of science, medicine and professions pioneered, for example, by Gieryn (1999), and taken up more recently by Brosnan (2015) and Vuolanto et al. (2020), have drawn considerable attention to the processes of boundary division by which scientific disciplines and modern professions seek to maintain their autonomous position, defend their territory, and gain legitimacy. More precisely, in Gieryn’s (1999) theory, “boundary work” describes “the discursive attribution of selected qualities to scientists, scientific methods, and

scientific claims for the purpose of drawing a rhetorical boundary between science and some less authoritative residual non-science practitioners” (Gieryn, 1999, pp. 4-5). These boundary-setting discourses, then, not only put the seemingly non-science position of CAM in one of those methodological straightjackets and polarized representations, but also involve CAM researchers making conciliatory efforts by using scientific evidence (Zerbe, 2007) to counterbalance perceived biases among the wider scientific community and reframe their knowledge boundary by virtue of their stringency in adopting research methods.

Yet, CAM’s use is increasing fast throughout the world. Frequently, therefore, sociological studies have examined different CAM modalities in their professionalization across societies, for example, the US (Falci et al., 2016), Australia (Wiese & Oster, 2010), Canada (Kelner et al., 2006), and European countries (Busato et al., 2006), including attitudes of Arab and Jewish patients referred to primary care clinics (Ben-Arye et al., 2009), or reporting Type 2 diabetes (Ben-Arye et al., 2011). While this formal list of sociological studies is by no means exhaustive, the increasing popularity of CAM is enough to provide the building blocks for wider societal trends while also embracing a consumer-driven approach to medical care (Emmerton et al., 2012; Sibbritt et al., 2016).

Because of this groundswell of appeal in wider society, it is no surprise to see a substantial amount of CAM research articles gaining a foothold in some academic publishing venues. In selecting the most suitable venue for their work, many CAM scholars are not just simply anxious to bring insights into therapies, protocols, and strategies and their responsible integration with mainstream medicine, they are also contending with the often-cited, highly competitive regime of ‘publish or perish’ (Hyland, 2015) that is imposed on all scholars all over the world (Salager-Meyer, 2014) and expects them to rapidly publish their research results in *h*-index, international (English-medium) journals in order to gain tenure, secure funding, and advance careers, among other objectives (Guraya et al., 2016; Hyland, 2015, 2023; van Dalen & Henkens, 2012). But at the same time as facing the pressures by institutions, funders, or other stakeholders, CAM scholars must also face the highly competitive landscape of mainstream biomedical research dominating the digitally transformed system of scholarly medical publishing through the formal and less formal modes of communication (Tessuto, 2025).

In such a highly-competitive academic environment, then, scholarly publishing emerges as “the system which both creates knowledge and distributes rewards to those who are most successful at it” (Hyland, 2023, p. 2), and points to how the modern “attention economy,” a concept borrowed from the world of marketing and business (Hyland, 2023, p. 1), increasingly works for scholars “to gain the attention, and approval, of reviewers, editors, readers, funders and

promotion boards” (Hyland, 2023, p. 2). By extension, this concept translates into a specific competitive mechanism of allocation constructed via the “scarcity” of a desired good within the academia, as with scholars competing for limited material goods, such as grants, royalties, or jobs, or immaterial goods, such as attention, visibility, or recognition (Arora-Jonsson et al., 2023; Krücken, 2019), thereby encapsulating the intense pressure on academics to succeed, to meet expectations and to compete with others.

By the same token, this competitive format tells us much about a wider, long-established societal trend toward “marketization” of the academy, which Bauwens et al. (2023, pp. 1-2) define along “two related dimensions: the commodification of academic output and the ‘managerialization’ of academic governance,” suggesting the increased tendency to treat scholarly output as these mechanisms are made all the easier by the digitized system of scholarly outputs where, as noted, CAM also takes the field; they also hinge upon digitally published research articles that are created and exchanged for audience attention and compete for new knowledge and the attendant recognition, making the case that digital “research articles are products competing for readers’ limited attention in a context of massively greater competition” (Hyland, 2023, p. 1).

As a result of all this, the originality of CAM research is of high value in a context where CAM scholars not only must cut the mustard and share their knowledge in the cutthroat culture of academic writing, but they must also work twice as hard to survive on a very uneven playing field to secure their own professional ‘boundaries’ and protect their knowledge and expertise against their mainstream, biomedical competitors. Their writing, therefore, is in large part a matter of designing research content that is effective in carving out a knowledge space, establishing their own credibility, and competing for visibility of, and attention for, the topic of their expertise among members of the scientific community. In other words, there is the need for writers to make the most persuasive argument they can for themselves and their work using the patterns of language which connect their texts with the rhetorical promotion of their research output and express the criteria for academic success.

When it comes to the lexis of promotional rhetoric for academic persuasion, mostly in the field of medicine, instances of evaluative/subjective language to promote, glamorize, or publicize aspects of research have been noticed in academic discourse under various labels. Millar et al. (2019) refer to these instances as ‘hype’ in the genre of Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs), while others suggest ‘drama’ words (Wheatley, 2014), ‘value-laden vocabulary’ (Fraser & Martin, 2009), ‘positive words’ (Vinkers et al., 2015) and ‘superlatives’ (McCarthy, 2015). So, for instance, Fraser and Martin (2009)

found a significant increase in 21 ‘biased adjectives’ such as *important*, *critical* and *original* in their clinical research journals published in PubMed between 1985 and 2005; Vinkers et al. (2015) found almost the same—25 positive-sounding words like *amazing*, *innovative* running in titles and abstracts of papers published in PubMed between 1974 and 2014; and more recently Hyland and Jiang (2021) picked up on several different hyping terms in their Covid19 papers, equally pointing to an increase in hyping in the period under consideration.

Against this background, the current study probes into the persuasive arsenal of scholars to raise their visibility as experts in the discipline and keep readers’ attention to their research work. To this end, the study conducts a quantitative and qualitative discourse analysis of CAM research articles to see how and to what extent scholars use an interpersonal and evaluative system of linguistic expressions to signal their understandings of the materials, and how they exploit persuasive practices of the genre to build their own authority and credibility—and, ultimately, their visibility that compete for this attention.

3. Method

3.1. Corpus

The data source for this study came from a synchronic, randomized corpus of 30 English-medium, multiple-authored academic research articles (RAs) written by internationally dispersed scholars from the field and available from *three Open Access reputable peer-reviewed journals*—namely, *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies (CMT)*, *JAMA Network Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM)*, and *Evidence-Based Integrative Medicine (EBIM)*, published previously as the *Journal of Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine (JEBCAM)*. Three equal-size corpora were built from this field over a five-year period (from January 2019 to January 2024), with each corpora containing 10 RAs in the category of ‘Original Articles’ / ‘Original Investigation’ to form a corpus of 30 samples in all. In reporting on alternative, complementary, and integrative medicine topics alongside their interventions, practices, and products, all the articles tied academic writers to the standard Introduction-Method-Results-Discussion (IMRD) macrostructure of research article writing, as necessary to lay down a hypothesis-driven and evidence-based position on the topics under scrutiny, providing a principled way to see how CAM writers situate their work to mark their participation in their discipline-specific practices. Articles were randomly downloaded from these community-recognized repositories, converted into electronic format, removed of reference sections and visuals, and finally computed by *AntConc* (Anthony, 2018) for a 142,872 running token corpus (Table 1).

Table 1
Characteristics of the Corpus

Journal title	Years	Papers	Tokens	Words	Sentences
BMC CMT	2019-2023	10	47,343	36,928	1,576
JAMA Network CAM	2019-2023	10	42,376	32,887	1,340
EBIM	2019-2023	10	53,153	44,303	1,746
Total	5	30	142.872	114.118	4.662

In terms of size and time span, this sample provides a broadly representative picture of language use across a reasonable spectrum of academic endeavour and in key areas of CAM research.

3.2. Analytical procedure

To explore these corpora in quantitative and qualitative terms, reference was made to Hyland's (2005a) interactional *stance* framework for evaluation in academic writing. In this framework, *stance* "involves 'positioning', or adopting a point of view in relation to both the issues discussed in a text and to others who hold points of view on those issues" (Hyland, 2005a, p. 176), and is one of "the most significant concepts in applied linguistics" (Hyland & Sancho Guinda, 2013, p. 1). This evaluative framework comprises three rhetorical components realized by target items—namely, *evidentiality* (hedges and boosters), *affect* (attitude markers), and *presence* (self-mentions), each with their own interpersonal resources writers can use to present propositional material and conduct interpersonal negotiations (Hyland, 2005a, p. 178-181), all while revealing "an act of identity" in academic discourse (Ivanič, 1998, p. 32) or "styles" for "evaluation and the values to which people commit themselves" in identity-marking schemes (Fairclough, 2003, p. 17). Of these target items, hedges were removed from the count as their function is not strictly related to promotional language, and hence do not fall into line with the current analysis. This framework was supplemented by reference to the literature on the use of hyperbolic subjective language for promotional rhetoric, most typically "hyperbolic terms" realized by adjectives stressing value such as *important*, *critical*, *original* (Millar et al., 2019), alongside 'drama words' (Weathley, 2014,) and 'positive words' (Vinkers et al., 2015) such as *amazing*, *novel*, *innovative*, all while recognizing a cline between moderate and exaggerated promotion.

Target items in the current corpora were searched using *AntConc* (Anthony, 2018), manually examined and counted for each concordance to establish that the candidate feature was performing a proper stance and or hyping function across the argumentative structure of research papers. Individual items were

compiled in a list of frequency counts and used as a springboard to a qualitative and quantitative analysis of the samples.

4. Results and discussion

Based on this data analytical procedure, it is now possible to look at how evaluative linguistic resources operate in both frequency and function across the corpus samples.

4.1. Stance markers by frequency: overall corpus findings

Upon close inspection of the sampled texts, a total of 1,228 instances of potential stance markers were identified across all sections of CAM research articles (Table 2 below), where they average 10.76 cases per 1000 words or 40.93 per article. Already at first sight, such instances demonstrate the importance writers attached to evaluating material and conveying an explicit stance or position towards the sources of the evaluation and the readers in the interactional and persuasive nature of the genre.

Table 2
Frequency of Interactional Boosters, Affect and Presence Markers Across Corpus Sections of CAM RAs

RA Sections	Markers				
		Boosters	Affect	Presence	Total
Introduction	<i>f</i>	229	264	21	514
	%	44.55	51.36	4.09	100
Method	<i>f</i>	10	13	9	32
	%	31.25	40.63	28.12	100
Results	<i>f</i>	19	15	27	61
	%	31.15	24.59	44.26	100
Discussion	<i>f</i>	265	281	39	585
	%	45.3	48.03	6.67	100
Conclusion	<i>f</i>	12	24	0	36
	%	33.33	66.67	0	100
Total	<i>f</i>	535	597	96	1.228
	%	43.56	48.62	7.82	100

Overall, the frequency counts in Table 2 show that writers make far more use of all evaluative resources in the 'Introduction' and 'Discussion' sections, with almost nine out of ten markers occurring in these sections alone. A closer examination of these counts also reveals that *affect* markers are the most popular choice overall, accounting for almost one half of markers employed (48.62%), followed by *boosters* (43.56%), with *presence* markers trailing

behind (7.82%). Interestingly, this rhetorical pattern is generally evident in the Introduction, Discussion and Conclusion sections to varying degrees, as in Conclusion, where *affect* counts for more than two thirds, while *presence* is completely absent. But, this is not necessarily apparent in other sections like Results, where writers turn to *presence* markers as a first choice (44.26%), or the Method section, where *presence* markers account for almost one third of all stance markers, albeit taking second place to *affect* markers.

The reason for this uneven distribution of stance markers not only appears to be consistent with writers' personal choices but also with the amount of rhetorical work that is done across article sections where, as mentioned, the IMRD research report macrostructure stands out as a basic form to perform different discourse functions. For instance, Introductions aimed to motivate and justify the authors' work and usually involved establishing the significance of the broader field by stating an opportunity (or gap in the research), a problem the research responds to constructively, or a question the research answers or deepens, in what typifies the elements in Swales' (2004) CARS model. Discussions served to situate the findings and the generality of the conclusion within the field by interpreting the results in light of previous research and making a case for the results as significant, limited, or altogether failed (Basturkmen, 2012). This made the use of stance features far greater in these sections.

4.2. Stance markers by function

We now look at how different interactional stance features perform their discourse functions in the texts, and how they help writers accomplish their rhetorical and persuasive purposes in the genre.

4.2.1. Boosters

Boosters, the second most frequent items in the corpus (43.56%), were more heavily packed in Discussions (45.30 %) and Introductions (44.55 %) and far less prevalent in Conclusions (33.33 %). Table 3 (below) provides a breakdown of the overall frequency counts of these devices employed throughout the corpus, where stance was most usually determined by the frequency of lexical verbs appearing in an 'evaluative *that*-clause' construction (Hyland & Tse, 2005) to give greater prominence to writers commenting on and evaluating the accuracy of what they present in their prior or current research.

The crucial importance of boosters in this form of academic writing lies in the fact that they help writers persuade peers of the correctness of their claims by investing statements with the confidence of reliability of knowledge and representing strong claims about states of affairs, all while stressing shared information and effecting solidarity in ways that they play a part in the social

negotiation of knowledge (Hyland, 2005a). This is true in the current data where boosters support the writer's argument in one of two ways: (1) emphasize the strength of the writer's commitment to a proposition, and (2) enable the writer to comment impersonally on the validity of propositions.

Table 3
*Breakdown of the Overall
Frequency Counts of Boosters*

RA Sections	Boosters	
Introduction	<i>f</i>	229
	%	44.55
Method	<i>f</i>	10
	%	31.25
Results	<i>f</i>	19
	%	31.15
Discussion	<i>f</i>	265
	%	45.3
Conclusion	<i>f</i>	12
	%	33.33
Total	<i>f</i>	535
	%	43.56

Table 3 continued
*Lexical and Grammatical Realizations of
Boosters*

Lexical & grammatical realizations	<i>f</i>	%
Modal auxiliary verbs	64	25.79
Lexical verbs	167	26.92
Adjectives	98	15.89
Adverbs	84	11.40
Nouns	73	13.64
Miscellaneous	49	6.36
Total	535	100

First, boosters emphasize the strength of the writer's commitment to a proposition and thereby seek to convince readers by their assurance in the fact-like certainty. This rhetorical work can be seen in these typical cases where writers employ a variety of boosting expressions to emphasize the epistemic conviction they wish to attach to their arguments, as in examples (1) and (4) with the writers being confident about 'yoga producing a desired effect in post-traumatic stress disorder', or about 'steroid drugs having serious side effects on osteoporosis, myopathy, and so on':

- (1) **It is evident** that effectiveness of yoga to treat post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) is growing. (CAM: Introduction)
- (2) As we have seen, the threshold for reporting serious adverse events, **quite simply**, is high. (CAM: Discussion)
- (3) It is **indeed the case** that rhinoviruses, influenza viruses, and coronaviruses are diagnosed in acute respiratory infections. (CMT: Introduction)
- (4) But **what is certain** is that steroid drugs have serious side effects such as osteoporosis and fractures, immunosuppression, myopathy, cardiovascular disease, glaucoma and . . . (CMT: Discussion)

- (5) **Undoubtedly**, establishing the identity and purity of a botanical drug relies on chemical characterization of molecules in the mixture . . . (EBIM: Introduction)
- (6) Further studies in clinical trials **should definitely** explore preclinical and clinical data regarding the herbal medicines described here. (EBIM: Discussion)

By projecting a good dose of optimism about the issues at stake, these writers are therefore able to present information as consensually given by relying more on shared background.

The second way that writers employ boosters is to comment impersonally on the validity of propositions. This kind of commitment comes through particularly in Discussion sections where authors position their study results in ways that are adequately controlled (compared to a placebo or conventional medicine), randomized, or statistically based to describe and interpret the effect reported in research as confidently and accurately as possible. This, then, allows writers to follow the same standards and evidence threshold as those of mainstream ('hard' science) medicine, meaning that the writers are principally concerned with conferring validity to their investigation, generating sound and objective evidence regarding an alternative/complementary treatment, and getting the reader understand and accept the veracity of their empirical data in terms of 'factive' statements. Their committal stance, in other words, is consistent with the epistemological assumption of positivism in research and scientific inquiry whereby only observable facts obtained from experience, experiments, or scientific methods can be genuine knowledge claims (Cohen et al., 2013).

By so doing, writers in the examples below relied heavily on a combination of 'abstract rhetors' (underlined) and boosters to present a view where a research entity, for instance, 'randomized clinical trials' in (8), takes responsibility for the asserted proposition and supports the reliability of their empirical claims with certainty of knowledge. So, it is easy to see how these writers use boosters to spotlight the strength of warrants with evidentiality verbs like *show* and *establish*, suggesting the efficacy of the connection between data and claims and spilling proof over into their arguments. Such is example (7), where writers invest their statements of findings with a guarantee of reliable knowledge, in this case that 'oxidative stress is one of the contributing factors for the development of oral infections', or express the certainty about expected outcomes with a modal *will* in example (12), in this case foretelling with shrewd inference from observable facts what is predictable about the 'human body adapting to TEAS intervention and bearing insensibility to pain condition':

- (7) These data **clearly show** that oxidative stress is one of the key etiological factors in etiopathogenesis of oral infections. (CAM: Discussion)
- (8) 73 IBS randomized clinical trials **proved** that the magnitude of the pooled placebo response rate in pharmacological trials in IBS was 27.3% for the global improvement responder end point. (CAM: Discussion)
- (9) This meta-analysis of 26 studies of music interventions provides **plain evidence** that music interventions are associated with clinically significant changes in mental HRQOL. (CMT: Discussion)
- (10) This research has **established** that the prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) is the final fever mediator in the brain, especially in the preoptic area of the anterior hypothalamus. (CMT: Discussion)
- (11) The results (Fig. 3A and B) **demonstrate** that the tested extracts displayed inhibition of COX-1 and COX-2 enzymes in a concentration dependent manner being more selective towards COX-2 enzyme. (EBIM: Discussion)
- (12) Repeated transcutaneous electrical acupoint stimulation (TEAS) intervention over a long period of time or at short intervals **will** cause the body to adapt to TEAS and thus become highly tolerant of analgesia. (EBIM: Discussion)

While all these cases show that the writers' new claims are unequivocally and immediately apparent for readers to accept, they also conjure up a self-restrained excitement or 'drama' (Weathley, 2014), as writers are now setting great store by their new findings and presenting themselves at the cutting edge of CAM research.

4.2.2. Boosters and self-mentions

As well as foregrounding data, procedures, or results by abstract rhetors and securing evidential reliability of their claims, writers do not shy away from a more personal style to adopt a particular stance to material by self-mentions, articulating a "discoursal self" (Ivanič, 1998, p. 25) and "authorial identity" (Hyland, 2005a, p. 181; Hyland, 2005b, p. 53) together when they seek to position themselves in relation to their current work and discipline:

- (13) In **our** research, **we have demonstrated** that cognitive damage by ketamine is clearly associated with its effects on major neurochemicals such as acetylcholine. (EBIM: Discussion)
- (14) **We strongly believe** that inflammation is a major culprit in arthritis, lupus, high blood pressure, migraines, rheumatoid arthritis, Chron's disease, Alzheimer's disease, irritable bowel syndrome, colitis, tendonitis. (CMT: Discussion)

- (15) In **our** randomized clinical trial of 74 patients with depression (authors' quote) **we found** noticeable differences in adverse event rates between the intervention (specific auricular acupuncture) and control (nonspecific auricular acupuncture) groups . . . (CAM: Discussion)

More precisely in these cases, we find authors claiming propriety and competence of what they report in the current study, as in example (13), with the writers staking out an individual position and data-supported claim about 'cognitive damage by ketamine having tangible effects on neurochemicals', or in example (14) moving from data-supported claims to construe a high personal commitment to the proposition that 'inflammation is the major cause of arthritis, lupus' or other medically diagnosed conditions, or even in (15) where writers give prominence to self-citation by sketching background to previously published work, in this case doing research in patients randomly assigned to an experimental group and move things forward in the current study.

4.2.3. Putting it all together

It therefore becomes clear that when writers strengthen their arguments with forms like *find*, *show*, *clearly* in the examples mentioned (7-15), they are not only describing the rationality and objectivity of their epistemological inquiries that are, for many, the epitomes of scientific research, but also making the most persuasive case for the originality or value of their research findings to the wider scientific community, including an audience of mainstream biomedical colleagues likely to be skeptical about such a value. Writers do so by legitimizing the validity and credibility of 'new' knowledge claims that emerge from the problems they investigate, the methodologies they employ, the data they analyze and, in our case, the significant outcomes they write up, thus establishing their authority and expertise to conduct significant research and contribute 'new' knowledge to such a community. Of course, claims here become robust and credible by the very fact of publishing articles in journals that operate a peer review quality threshold, and *a fortiori* ensure that unwarranted claims are not published and that 'truth claims are relevant, or unique', or are removed from unethical and questionable research practices, such as 'plagiarism' (Tessuto, 2024b). Equally importantly, however, legitimizing credibility is a measure of how well the writers can provide the best evidence to be implemented into practice by key stakeholders, including patients, medical doctors, therapists (e.g., mind-body health specialists), research boards, and so on, who are involved all along the whole research process, from defining the research question, deciding on the proceeding, member checking the analyses to co-authoring the publication of the results.

Yet, gaining credit by getting peer-reviewed articles published is by no means the end of the matter. As noted, the challenges for “academic productivity” in the publish or perish culture (van Dalen & Henkens, 2012, p. 1283) and for competition in the “attention economy” (Hyland, 2023, p. 1) also result in extraordinary efforts by CAM writers to make their research output stand out in the noise of publishing modes and formats that are made increasingly available by medical science/data/knowledge digital platforms. Whether these scholars may use different media channels to increase their research visibility and impact long after publication is not known. However, framing arguments in the most convincing way (e.g., *This paper clearly demonstrates that*) sends clear signals of CAM scholars being at pains to raise their visibility and impact by showcasing the value of their findings to their peers and other like-minded audiences, ultimately ensuring that their work gets seen, read, and cited, amidst that noise. So while CAM scholars spare no effort to gain audiences’ attention drop by drop through the persuasive force of their arguments and live their academic life within their comfort zone, they also seem to do so with the recognition that greater research visibility, impact and citations of their published article will work towards different outcomes in terms of career growth, such as when applying for grants, or promotions; in other words, competing for material (e.g., grants) or immaterial goods (e.g., attention).

This is where the ‘attention’ mechanism works for CAM writers to preemptively outperform others through maximizing and hence promoting their ‘own’ output to impact success. It operates so that the axiom ‘publish or perish’ of their academic professional life will stray towards the realms of ‘be visible or vanish’, ‘be cited or die’, or ‘promote or perish’ in this kind of hustle and bustle of digital knowledge market. And we can see this in more competitive, market-like or “managerial styles” (Fairclough, 2003, p. 9) of treating the (CAM) academy through the discourse that ensues and is gradually instilled into the social identity of CAM scholars writing in the genre to promote themselves and their research ‘output’ in a way that is analogous to promoting goods. So, there is now a form of “interdiscursivity” (Fairclough, 2003, p. 35; Bhatia, 2017, p. 34) weaving through the published genre when CAM scholars present their article findings ideationally to highlight their accuracy and reliability and conduct social relations with colleagues.

In sum, what CAM writers do when they seek to persuade the wider audiences to assent to the significance and certainty of their knowledge claims by boosters while competing for visibility, impact and attention of their output is to follow in the footsteps of fellow colleagues from across disciplines where hyperbolic and promotional strategies come up. Such is, for instance, Hyland and Jiang’s (2021) larger study of Covid19 papers, where research is found to be more strenuously ‘hyped’ both qualitatively and quantitatively, or Millar et al.’s (2019) qualitative and quantitative study of hyperbolic language in

reports of randomized controlled trials, or even Wang and Yand's (2015) study on promotional elements of research in introductions to applied linguistics research articles. Yet what it amounts to in this study is that CAM writers are found to employ promotional and hyperbolic language in moderation rather than embellishing as compared to their mainstream counterparts because, as mentioned, they are forced to steer a steady course along the lines of objectivity and credibility.

4.2.4. Affect

Hyperbolic and promotional practices become more visible when CAM scholars are much more oriented towards evaluating claims by *affect* markers, which account for the most frequent evaluative stance items throughout the corpus (48.62%), and again particularly represented in Discussions (48.03%) and Introductions (51.36%), though it might be worth mentioning that in Conclusion sections there are proportionally twice as many *affect* markers (66.67%) as *boosters* (33.33%).

Table 4

Breakdown of the Overall Frequency Counts of Affect

RA Sections	Affect Markers
Introduction	<i>f</i> 264
	% 51.36
Method	<i>f</i> 13
	% 40.63
Results	<i>f</i> 15
	% 24.59
Discussion	<i>f</i> 281
	% 48.03
Conclusion	<i>f</i> 24
	% 66.67
Total	<i>f</i> 597
	% 48.62

Table 4 continued

Lexical & grammatical realizations: Positive attitude markers in hyping function

Lexical and grammatical realizations	<i>f</i>	%
Adjectives	196	32.83
Adverbs	171	28.64
Nouns	110	18.43
Verbs	63	10.55
Phrases	57	9.55
Total	597	100

More precisely, Table 4 (below) shows the range and frequency of positively marked attitude items realized as adjectives, adverbs, nouns, verbs, and longer phrases for expressing the writer's affective perspectives and personal evaluations towards content and for moderately hyping up and promoting different facets of the authors' research, corroborating other studies where hyping practices are found in different types of academic discourse writings (Fraser & Martin, 2009; Hyland & Jiang, 2021; Millar et al., 2019; Vinkers et al.,

2015). This range of items means that when writers mark positive *affect* through a statement of personal judgement and appeal to shared values, hyping words and phrases make it harder for writers not to tap into their own knowledge of what is valued by the wider scientific community, and this contributes both to the interpersonal dimension of the ongoing discourse and the use of promotional language intended to persuade. With that, though, discrete hyping forms in Table 4 (below) inevitably conceal the fact that they often perform more than one function because writers can address the ‘importance’, ‘quality’, ‘novelty’, and variations thereof, when they are rhetorically promoting their paper through a positive attitude of some kind.

Consistent with this, evaluatively positive items like *crucial*, *significant*, or variations thereof, whether or not pre-modified by other intensifying resources like *very*, are those which are more commonly relied on by the writers to convey the ‘importance’ or ‘weight’ of their current research and make the message convincing in a *prominence-* or *salience-level* marking function. We can see this in the examples below across mainly Introduction and Discussion sections, where writers are heavily invested in spelling out what is relevant about their empirical study and staking out their scientific claims and arguments to tangible topics, as in (16) and (19), where issues of ‘metabolic and anti-inflammatory potential of leucocada’ or ‘a test compound in paw edema’ are presented as ‘sufficiently great or important’ to nudge positive attention spillover effects on the authors’ work:

- (16) We believe that the metabolic content and the anti-inflammatory potential of *A. leucoclada* is of **crucial importance**. (CAM: Introduction)
- (17) Herein, we introduce a **very important** placebo intervention for comparison with flotation-REST. (CMT Introduction)
- (18) Overall, this study underlines the **importance** of maintaining healthy ROM, especially in subjects who already show signs of impairment. (CAM: Discussion)
- (19) The test compound A showed a **highly significant** ($P < 0.001$) decrease in paw edema ranging from 46 to 68% during the 1st hour of the experiment as compared to standard drug ibuprofen (57%). (CMT: Discussion)
- (20) This marks a **substantial breakthrough** because the benefit of other anti-inflammatory therapies among patients with COVID-19 (e.g., dexamethasone, tocilizumab) is **highly** dependent on severity of illness ... (EBIM: Introduction)
- (21) The use of TEAS **greatly** reduces the occurrence of OS and central nervous system damage during surgery and, **significantly**, has a brain protective effect. (EBIM: Discussion)

While the combination of boosting verbal items here (e.g., *show*, *underline*) reinforces epistemic conviction in claims and a clear assurance of importance in different parts of an argument, it is easy to see how positive personal evaluations carry promotional values, enabling writers to express their affective position to the topics they hype and to bring readers round to their evaluative perspective. The *saliency-level* driver of the rhetorical attention mechanism explains why writers mostly care about hyping in Introduction and Discussion sections, where they claim centrality for their research topics as in example (16), or situate the findings and the generality of the conclusion within their study as in (22), and in this way, they encourage readers to accept that the domains they have identified are worthwhile to read about.

In addition, other opportunities arise from across article sections. Here, writers are more likely concerned with emphasizing the ‘tangible benefit’ or ‘utility’ of their research that is worthy of recognition by readers landing on the article page, with lemmas like *necessary* and *effective* being used to that rhetorical effect, as in:

- (22) This work will be **necessary** to investigate the function of individual active components of AVE and to identify their **effective** mechanism of action. (CAM: Introduction)
- (23) Taken together, the present study suggests a **potent** effect of CLE to prevent neuroinflammatory diseases. (CAM: Discussion)
- (24) Sleep disturbance is a complicated mechanism, and the TST is a **useful** method to evaluate sleep deprivation. (CAM: Conclusion)
- (25) Thus, *Hericium erinaceus* mycelium is a **valid** dual-function supplement for sleep disruption **improvement** while **sustaining** anxiolytic effects. (CMT: Introduction)
- (26) The results obtained in the present in vitro study **contribute to the beneficial** effects of these plant extracts on symptoms of acute respiratory infections. (CMT: Conclusion)
- (27) The **efficacy** of tuina combined with yijinjing on soft tissue hardness and AROM can be clearly observed by the electronic spine measuring device and digital algometer. (CMT: Introduction)
- (28) As seen, propofol and remifentanyl pumps can **effectively** avoid cerebral vascular dilation caused by inhalation anesthesia. (EBIM: Discussion)

Just as these writers relied on hypes to address the issue of their research contribution to knowledge head on, while foregrounding their ideas, claims or findings in positivist paradigm, so too they take a stand and align their readers with what is being presented around those attitudinal meanings.

Of course, the Method and Result sections are also targeted to spill over into the positive effects of the authors' research, though hyping to a much lesser degree, as in:

- (29) Subjects' heart rate, blood pressure, height, weight, waist and hip circumferences were measured by our **experienced** practitioners. (EBIM: Method)
- (30) The **strength** of this study is the random process of patients. (CMT: Method)
- (31) **To facilitate** the mechanism of action of pelargonium extract against influenza virus, we performed **systematic** time-of-addition assays as well as . . . (CAM: Method)
- (32) **Strikingly**, equivalence analyses of change scores were **significantly** different between the TCTSY and CPT groups, . . . (CMT: Results)
- (33) The TCTSY treatment completion rate was 42.6% and is the **most valuable** finding, given the limited engagement in and completion of EBTs. (CAM: Results)

As we see, these hypes most often seek to establish the value or importance of a well-planned 'research design' in terms of its components employed in the investigation alongside a factual presentation of findings, meaning that the main function shared by Method and Results is to provide the most informative description of the researchable problem in support of accurate data analysis and to contribute something 'new'.

But, given the very role of accounting research for advancing 'new' knowledge, writers do not shy away from emphasizing the intrinsic 'quality' of their published research based on the most reliable indicator of research 'distinction' or 'novelty', that is, how the interpretations and conclusions of the study 'make a difference' to the existing body of literature, as in (34-37), or highlighting their contributory 'potential' for future research based on a set of self-evident claims, as in (38-40), thus showing how they care about hyping and bring the empirical reality of their study to the wider effects of attention seeking:

- (34) This is **the first well-designed** study from a general population and including healthy individuals published to date, making the findings **more interesting**. (CAM: Introduction)
- (35) **Unique** manufacturing issues will be addressed throughout this research. (CAM: Introduction)
- (36) Interestingly, this study is **the first** to report GC-MS investigation of *A. leucoclada*. (CMT: Results)

- (37) The present study came up with **novel** and **robust** findings. Both the compounds were found effective therapeutic agents (EBIM: Discussion)
- (38) In conclusion, cassava represents a **highly promising** crop with **considerable** commercial potential owing to its **exceptional** nutritional profile . . . (CAM: Conclusion)
- (39) **Remarkably**, these findings present *A. dubius* as a **promising** candidate that provide several leads to develop potential **novel** agents for management of AD. (EBIM: Conclusion)
- (40) **This is a critical next step to shed further light on** this perplexing clinical issue and research question. (CMT: Discussion)

Once again, we see the tendency to hype around something as a signal of the highly competitive nature of medical journal publishing, where CAM scholars continue to face challenges, and the potentially huge risks and rewards of various kinds associated with the imperatives of maximizing visibility and impact and competing for academic success in the attention-based mechanism. By creating their papers to contain hyping items and to rhetorically respond to these imperatives, CAM scholars not only offer other effective ways to stand out from the crowd and showcase the value of research to their peers and others, but also display their professional knowledge and status that promotes their scientific expertise and credibility in the field—their work ‘stands on its own merit’. This is, in other words, the authority and visibility that keep growing among CAM scholars who have demonstrated their credibility to act effectively in their own niche and to make significant, original contributions as ‘new’ knowledge in the fast-moving digital publishing market. But, genres, even the apparent conservative scientific paper, are sites of constancy as well as movement, so credibility that is now being promoted through hyping practices and persuasively represented to audiences is no less material to account for the level (constraints and allowances) of social practices and interdiscursive relations between genres, discourses and styles (Bhatia, 2017; Fairclough, 2003), and therefore point yet to the same tendency towards a competitive, self-motivating mindset now cropping up in the interactional, *affect* features of the published genre.

And it is little wonder that harnessing research to promotional goals and the marketing funnel is now making CAM products a multi-billion dollar business, according to some market analysis reports (*Complementary And Alternative Medicine Market Analysis Report 2024-2030*), suggesting that lack of profitability should not be a reason companies do not take up these products for research and development activities, in the same way as market players are constantly seeking for establishing their dominance in the market and gaining competitive edge over others. Clearly, profitability overall is much larger for

conventional medication than for CAM products, but the increasing consumer demand for 'natural' or 'holistic' methods across pluralistic Western societies and government initiatives to promote and offer CAM services and therapies send a clear signal of the ways writers cannot help but respond to economic and social forces of the market economy of healthcare and hype what they have to hand in the discourses they produce.

5. Conclusion

In this study I have sought to explore how CAM genre writers deploy evaluative and interpersonal resources of stance to represent themselves, their research, and their readers at a time when alternative/complementary medical research and practices are struggling to gain ground in diverse meaning-making ontologies of institutionalized bio-medicine. The analysis of *boosters* and positive attitude markers for evidentiality and *affect* meaning-making, however relatively conventional in the genre, has been shaped by an awareness of writers to supply as many cues as are needed to secure readers' understanding and acceptance of their arguments and claims, while conveying their professional credibility and expertise in terms of the propositions they frame for the wider scientific community to see as most persuasive. This array of discourse conventions is inevitably selective of how disciplinary and cultural values of non-mainstream medicine are reflected and carried through the persuasive goals of the academic reporting genre.

Beyond this line-up of discourse conventions, the analysis has shown that the imperatives for academic success in today's business-like and competitive scholarly publishing increasingly involve CAM scholars relying on their persuasive arsenal to stake knowledge claims for their significance, originality, or utility and to heavily invest in research promotion to maximize their visibility and impact, ultimately cutting through the noisy space of digital publishing and getting noticed. This writers' tendency to rhetorically emphasize the strength of their claims and promote the value of their work does not mean detracting from impartiality of science despite an insatiable thirst for research marketability. Rather, their promotional strategies serve as a proxy for the safety and efficacy of new alternative diagnosis and treatments they propose and practice for a broad range of audiences using sound and rigorous research methods that are useful, relevant, safe, and cost-effective. This way of 'seeing' promotion in texts through congruent discourse analytical realizations goes some way towards helping us understand how writers as researchers exploit the generic and rhetorical resources available to them, in an effort to raise attention for their work. And, this turns on how academic writing in this highly competitive genre is not static or fixed but is constantly evolving to suit new purposes and social conditions.

So, where the scientific rhetoric of alternative/complementary research promises to bring safety and efficacy to non-mainstream practice of medicine and healthcare, what we see basically is CAM scholars' discourse employing epistemologies of legitimation and professional identity to secure their positions. At the same time, they are negotiating their relational positionality *vis à vis* biomedicine, relaxing or breaking down rhetorical boundaries to reconcile CAM and biomedical practices without undermining the integrity of either domain.

As a follow up to this study, the current data could be exploited for a more detailed (quantitative) comparison with linguistic and discursive strategies employed by writers in mainstream medical research articles. What emerges from these findings is that the time is ripe to make room for a new academic culture where CAM researchers can have their voice heard without prejudice and join the ranks of the 'trusted messengers' of medical research.

The Author

Girolamo Tessuto (Email: girolamo.tessuto@unicampania.it) is Full Professor of English Language, Linguistics and Translation at the Department of Precision Medicine of the University of Campania 'Luigi Vanvitelli' where he is also Director of the Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Language and Medicine (CIRLaM), formerly Centre for Research in Language and Law (CRILL). Besides memberships of several academic and professional associations, he is editorial board member of various international English linguistics journals, and chief editor of the *Medical Discourse and Communication* internationally peer-reviewed series published by Cambridge Scholars in the UK. His research interests focus primarily on (critical) discourse analysis of academic, professional, and institutional genres in medical, healthcare, and legal contexts, English for Specific Purposes, English for Academic Purposes, and specialized translation. His published academic work comprises research monographs and several different publications appearing as research articles, book chapters, co-edited volumes, and book reviews.

References

- Adams, J., Andrews, G., Barnes, J., Broom, A., & Magin, P. (2012). Introduction. In J. Adams, G. Andrews, J. Barnes, A. Broom & P. Magin (Eds.), *Traditional, complementary and integrative medicine: An international reader* (pp. 1-7). Palgrave Macmillan.

- Arora-Jonsson, S., Brunsson, N., & Edlund, P. (2023). The construction of competition in public research funding systems. In B. Lepori, B. Jongbloed & D. Hicks (Eds.), *Handbook of public funding of research*, (pp. 172-184). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Baronov, D. (2008). Biomedicine: An ontological dissection. *Theoretical Medicine and Bioethics*, 29(4), 235-254.
- Basturkmen, H. (2012). A genre-based investigation of discussion sections of research articles in dentistry and disciplinary variation. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 11, 2, 134-144.
- Bauwens, T., Reike, D., & Calisto-Friant, M. (2023). Science for sale? Why academic marketization is a problem and what sustainability research can do about it. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 48, 100749.
- Ben-Arye, E., Karkabi, K., Karkabi, S., Keshet, Y., Haddad, M., & Frenkel, M. (2009). Attitudes of Arab and Jewish patients toward integration of complementary medicine in primary care clinics in Israel: A cross-cultural study. *Social Science & Medicine*, 68(1), 177-82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2008.10.004>
- Ben-Arye, E., Schiff, E., Karkabi, K., Keshet, Y., & Lev, E. (2011). Exploring association of spiritual perspectives with complementary medicine use among patients with type 2 diabetes in Israel. *Ethnicity & Health*, 16(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13557858.2010.510181>
- Beyerstein, B. L. (2001). Alternative medicine and common errors of reasoning. *Academic Medicine*, 76, 230-237.
- Bhatia, V. K. (2017). *Critical genre analysis: Investigating interdiscursive performance in professional communication*. Routledge.
- Brosnan, C. (2015). 'Quackery' in the academy? Professional knowledge, autonomy and the debate over complementary medicine degrees. *Sociology*, 49(6), 1047.
- Busato, A., Dönges, A., Herren, S., Widmar, M., & Marian, F. (2006). Health status and health care utilisation of patients in complementary and conventional primary care in Switzerland—an observational study. *Family Practice*, 23, 116-124.

- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2013). *Research methods in education*. Routledge.
- Davis, J. E. (2016). Biomedicine and its cultural authority. *The New Atlantis*, 48, 60-77.
- Emmerton, L., Fejzic, J., & Tett, S. E. (2012). Consumers' experiences and values in conventional and alternative medicine paradigms: a problem detection study (PDS). *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 10, 12-39.
- Fairclough, N. (2003). *Analysing discourse: Textual analysis for social research*. Routledge.
- Falci, L., Shi, Z., & Greenlee, H. (2016). Multiple chronic conditions and use of complementary and alternative medicine among US adults: Results from the 2012 National Health Interview Survey. *Preventing Chronic Disease*, 5(13), E61.
- Fraser, V. J., & Martin, J. G. (2009). Marketing data: Has the rise of impact factor led to the fall of objective language in the scientific article? *Respiratory Research*, 10, 35.
- Gieryn, T. F. (1999). *Cultural boundaries of science: Credibility on the line*. The University of Chicago Press.
- Grandinetti, D. (2000). Acupuncture in 2000: Working its way into mainstream medicine. *Medical Economics*, 77(15), 99-110.
- Guraya, S. Y., Norman, R. I., Khoshhal, K. I., Guraya, S. S., & Forgione, A. (2016). Publish or perish mantra in the medical field: A systematic review of the reasons, consequences and remedies. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Science* 32(6), 1562-1567.
- Hampshire, K., & Owusu, S. (2012). Grandfathers, Google, and dreams: Medical pluralism, globalization, and new healing encounters in Ghana. *Medical Anthropology*, 32, 247-65.
- Hyland, K. (2005a). Stance and engagement: A model of interaction in academic discourse. *Discourse Studies*, 7(2), 173-192.
- Hyland, K. (2005b). *Metadiscourse: Exploring interaction in writing*. Continuum.

- Hyland, K. (2015). *Academic publishing: Issues and challenges in the construction of knowledge*. Oxford University Press.
- Hyland, K. (2023). Academic publishing and the attention economy. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 64, 101253.
- Hyland, K., & Jiang, K. (2021). The Covid infodemic: Competition and the hyping of virus research. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 26(4), 444-468.
- Hyland, K., & Sancho Guinda, C. (Eds.). (2013). *Stance and voice in written academic genres*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hyland, K., & Tse, P. (2005). Hooking the reader: A corpus study of evaluative 'that' in abstracts. *Journal of English for Specific Purposes*, 24, 123-139.
- Ivanič, R. (1998). *Writing and identity: The discursual construction of identity in academic writing*. John Benjamins.
- Keating, P., & Cambrosio, A. (2003). *Biomedical platforms: Realigning the normal and the pathological in late-twentieth-century medicine*. MIT Press.
- Kelner, M., Wellman, B., Welsh, S., & Boon, H. (2006). How far can complementary and alternative medicine go? The case of chiropractic and homeopathy. *Social Science & Medicine*, 63, 2617-2627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2006.07.005>
- Krücken, G. (2019). Multiple competitions in higher education: A conceptual approach. *Innovation*, 23(2), 163-181.
- McCarthy, M. (2015). Superlatives are commonly used in news coverage of cancer drugs, study finds. *British Medical Journal*, 5803.
- Millar, N., Salager-Meyer, F., & Budgell, B. (2019). "It is important to reinforce the importance of": 'Hype' in reports of randomized controlled trials. *English for Specific Purposes*, 54, 139-151.
- Mortada, E. M. (2024). Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine in current medical practice. *Cureus* 10, 16(1), e52041.
- National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health, NCCIH. (2024). Complementary, alternative, or integrative health: What's in a name?

- National Institutes of Health—National Cancer Institute. (2023). <https://www.cancer.gov>
- Salager-Mayer, F. (2014). Writing and publishing in peripheral scholarly journals: How to enhance the global influence of multilingual scholars? *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 13, 78-82.
- Shih, C.-C., Su, Y.-C., Liao C.-C., & Lin, J.-G. (2010). Patterns of medical pluralism among adults: results from the 2001 National health interview survey in Taiwan. *BMC Health Services Research* 2010, 10, 191. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-10-191>
- Sibbritt, D., Millbank, J., Stuhmcke, A., Kaye, M., Karpin, I., & Wardle, J. (2016). The failure of contemporary law and regulation to keep pace with growing complementary medicine (CM) use: The significance of examining 'hidden' gaps in Australia's current regulatory and legislative infrastructure. *Advances in Integrative Medicine*, 3, 2, 43-4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aimed.2016.11.002>
- Swales, J. M. (2004). *Research genres: Explorations and applications*. Cambridge University Press.
- Tessuto, G. (2024a). *English for medicine: A toolkit for discourse and genre-based approaches to medical language and communication*. Giappichelli,
- Tessuto, G. (2024b.) Introduction. In G. Tessuto & M. Caraglia (Eds.), *Framing ethics and plagiarism in medical research writing and publishing* (pp. xiv-xxi). Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Tessuto, G. (2025). Digital medical science publishing and healthcare communication systems: Opportunities and challenges. In Carol A. Chapelle (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of applied linguistics* (forthcoming). Blackwell Publishing.
- US Complementary and Alternative Medicine Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report. (2024-2030). <https://www.grandviewresearch.com>
- van Dalen, H. P., & Henkens, K. (2012). Intended and unintended consequences of a publish-or-perish culture: A worldwide survey. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63, 1282-1293.

- Vinkers, C. H., Tjldink, J. K., & Otte, W. M. (2015). Use of positive and negative words in scientific PubMed abstracts between 1974 and 2014: Retrospective analysis. *British Medical Journal*, *351*, h6467.
- Vuolanto, P., Bergroth, H., Nurmi, J., & Salmenniemi, S. (2020). Reconfiguring health knowledges? Contemporary modes of self-care as 'everyday fringe medicine'. *Public Understanding of Science*, *29*(5), 508-523.
- Wang, W., & Yang, C. (2015). Claiming centrality as promotion in applied linguistics research article introductions. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, *20*, 162-175.
- Wheatley, D. (2014). Drama in research papers. *European Science Editing*, *40*(1), 14-16.
- Wiese, M., & Oster, C. (2010). 'Becoming accepted': The complementary and alternative medicine practitioners' response to the uptake and practice of traditional medicine therapies by the mainstream health sector. *Health*, *14*(4), 415-33.
- Yakoot, M. (2013). Bridging the gap between alternative medicine and evidence-based medicine. *Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapy*, *4*, 83-85.
- Zerbe, M. (2007). *Composition and the rhetoric of science: Engaging the dominant discourse*. Southern Illinois University Press.
- Anthony, L. (2018). *AntConc* (version 3.5.7) [computer software]. Waseda University.

Corpus sources

- BMC *Complementary Medicine and Therapies*. Available at <https://bmccomplementmedtherapies.biomedcentral.com/>
- JAMA *Network Complementary and Alternative Medicine* (CAM). Available at <https://jamanetwork.com/collections/5575/complementary-and-alternative-medicine>
- Journal of *Evidence-Based Integrative Medicine* (EBIM). Available at <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/chp>